

The Impact of Covid-19 on Small and Medium Enterprises in Bangladesh

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Abstract: The Covid-19 pandemic has disrupted the world economy in multifaceted ways. Although large businesses had some cushions to tackle the adverse impact of the pandemic, small, and medium enterprises (SMEs) suffered miserably. This paper seeks to examine the impact of the Covid-19 on SMEs in Bangladesh. Data has been collected through issuing a semi-structured questionnaire from 306 SMEs. We apply graphical presentation, descriptive statistics, and regression techniques to analyze the data. The major findings of the paper are as follows: (i) 87 percent of the SMEs reported a decline in sales; (ii) 92% of the SMEs reported that their production was disrupted owing to the problems with the supply chain; (iii) SMEs were successful in recovery to a significant extent; (iv) about 70% of the surveyed firms terminated employees during the pandemic, and more than half (54%) of the SMEs fired fewer than five employees; (v) an astounding number of firms (92%) canceled scheduled investments due to the pandemic; and (vi) 74% of the surveyed SMEs sought direct assistance from the government. Our regression analysis further reveals that SMEs which shifted business online, had large number of employees (big in size), and with enough liquidity cushion encountered a lower decline in income. However, firms that fired employees suffered heavily in terms of a decline in income. Based on the above findings, the research concludes that the SMEs in Bangladesh suffered a decline in sales significantly and experienced supply chain disruption during the Covid-19 pandemic. The research thus, recommends government intervention through fiscal and monetary means to reinvigorate the SME sector of the country.

Keywords: Bangladesh; Covid-19; pandemic; productivity; small and medium enterprises (SMEs)

1. Introduction

The novel coronavirus, known as Covid-19, has inscribed various scary marks on the global economy. It forced individuals to remain at home and pushed the government to issue directives for businesses and organizations to remain closed for an extended duration throughout 2020 and 2021. The epidemic profoundly impacted most sectors of the economy. Industrial operations ceased or remained limitedly active. Countries worldwide initiated social distancing policies to a varied extent; some enforced complete lockdowns, while others enacted partial restrictions or urged their citizens to remain indoors. This resulted in a decline in world GDP of an estimated 3% in 2020 and an accumulated loss of US\$9 trillion in 2020 and 2021¹. The unprecedented worldwide economic recession

resulting from the public health crisis is considered second only to the Great Depression of 1929².

The pandemic has affected business organizations in multifaceted ways, leading many organizations to the brink of bankruptcy. For example, a substantial increase of Chapter 11 filings by large US corporations was observed amidst generous incentive packages provided by the federal government through monetary and fiscal policies³. The existing firms are also facing adverse consequences, including slicing of cash flows and net income⁴. Uncertain business environment coupled with cash flow catastrophe is likely to prompt business organizations to be financially conservative. This may result in cut-off firms' discretionary costs and postpone long-term investment. Firms' conservative behavior imposed by financial constraints is likely to weaken the tempo of innovation in

green technologies, and thereby financial performance. The burgeoning literature examines the impacts of Covid-19 on various attributes of firms. For example, studies show that the pandemic has negatively affected firms' financial performance^{5),6)}. As a result, an increased number of firms resorted to leverage financing^{7),8)} which leads to the rise of firms' credit risk. Firms' augmented credit risks coupled with banks' conservative behavior implies that borrowers pay a risk premium. Ke⁹⁾ estimates that US public limited companies paid on average 172 basis-points extra cost on equity capital during the pandemic. Literature also examines the effects of COVID-19 on stock market returns. Xiong et al.¹⁰⁾, Harjoto et al.¹¹⁾, Aldhamari et al.¹²⁾, and Ramelli and Wagner¹³⁾ find that firms have experienced significant negative stock returns during the pandemic. Studies also reveal that the pandemic has substantially increased stock market crash risk¹⁴⁾ and financial fragility¹⁵⁾. Hence, firms intend to raise and hold more cash^{16),17)} and cut expenditures to match revenues¹⁸⁾. Although the extant literature mostly focuses on developed economies and large organizations, very few studies take the SMEs issues in the developing economies. For instance, Khalil et al.¹⁹⁾ analyze 96 SMEs across six developing countries and find that the digital technology has facilitated their survival during the pandemic, enhancing their resilience and ensuring their continuity. Engidaw²⁰⁾ observes that the crisis has inflicted devastation on Ethiopian small and large enterprises, rendering survival difficulty due to diminished revenue, job losses, and a deceleration of life, compounded by poor marketing performance, making it difficult to sustain their businesses. Lu et al.²¹⁾ conducted a study utilizing an online questionnaire and follow-up interviews with 4,807 SMEs in Sichuan, China. They identify that the SMEs challenges during the pandemic were related to job resumption and the requisite governmental measures. It was further found that most SMEs could not resume operations due to a lack of epidemic mitigation resources, staff unavailability, interrupted supply chains, and diminished market demand. Kahveci²²⁾ conducted interviews with foreign travelers in Turkey and found that survival remains the primary concern for small and medium-sized tourism enterprises, despite government relief initiatives, vaccination campaigns, and the relaxation of lockdown and travel restrictions. Sopha et al.²³⁾ perform an empirical investigation using a longitudinal study encompassing 30 conventional stores situated in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Empirical data were gathered through semi-structured interviews conducted in mid-2019 and mid-2020, reflecting the circumstances prior to and during the epidemic. The results indicate that the pandemic has caused disturbances in supply and demand, hence impacting operations. However, no such study was found in the context of Bangladesh. Despite the Covid-19 pandemic being a

universal threat to all economies, developing nations such as Bangladesh suffered significantly due to their substantial dependence on SMEs. A recent assessment by the International Cooperation Organization for Small and Medium Enterprises in Asia (ICOSA) indicates that SMEs contribute approximately 20.25% to the nation's GDP²⁴⁾. This sector comprises 17,384 microenterprises, 15,666 small enterprises, and 6,103 medium enterprises. SMEs constitute around 35 percent of overall employment in Bangladesh and approximately 45% of manufacturing value addition. This demonstrates that SMEs constitute a significant portion of Bangladesh's economy. The severity of the economic crisis induced by Covid-19 is fundamentally contingent upon the ability of SMEs to effectively address the negative repercussions of the epidemic. This bears the manifestation that assessing the impact of Covid-19 on SMEs is imperative. Given the above socio-cultural backdrop of Bangladesh and the existing research gap, our study aims to

- a. assess the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on SMEs in Bangladesh.
- b. assess the effects of the pandemic on the sales or revenues and dismissal of employees of SMEs
- c. identify factors that may mitigate the adverse impact of the pandemic on SMEs income
- d. recommend the needs and types of assistance required to reinvigorate the SME sector.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section two reviews the relevant literature. Section three describes the methodology used in this research. Section four interprets the results, whereas section five offer policy implications, and identifies future research areas, finally a summary of the research.

2. Literature review

Firms across the world, particularly small, and medium enterprises, were severely impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic. Lockdowns, travel bans, and changes in consumer behavior caused serious havoc to most business enterprises globally. Hence, various studies have been conducted in different countries to assess the type, nature, and degree of sufferings and what strategies firms and policymakers can adopt to mitigate the adverse effects of the pandemic. For instance, Yadav et al.²⁵⁾, in the context of the Indian handicraft industry, illustrate that this industry experienced extreme difficulties in continuing its operations, and in some cases, businesses were forced to halt production and operations. Similarly, Shafi et al.²⁶⁾ conducted research in the case of Pakistani SMEs and show that small enterprises in Pakistan had significant challenges, including financial difficulty, supply chain disruptions²⁷⁾, declining demand, lower sales, and lower profits. The study further shows that 83% of the businesses were not ready for this kind of scenario.

In the settings of Ethiopia, Engidaw²⁰⁾ contends that the pandemic caused suffering for many small enterprises. For instance, several SMEs experienced bankruptcies and found it very difficult to survive amidst an income slowdown, job cuts, and poor marketing performance. Likewise, Ma et al.²⁸⁾ document that the pandemic directly affected the product market of SMEs in China. Their research further finds that government instant policies greatly helped mitigate the negative impacts of the pandemic on SMEs. In another study in the context of China, Lu et al.²¹⁾ show, studying 4,807 SMEs in Sichuan province, that most the SMEs were unable to stay in business because of a lack of resources, a decline in the number of workers, a disrupted supply chain, and a decline in consumer demand. Additionally, many SMEs struggled with cash flow since they had several fixed expenses to pay for while receiving little to no income. On the other hand, Chen et al.²⁹⁾ reveal that local and regional lockdown in China resulted in a decrease in consumer demand. This research further shows that the payment delays as relief measures helped Chinese SMEs retain their cash flow while assisting them with operational recovery. Dai et al.⁴⁴⁾ examined the long-term impacts of COVID-19 lockdown on small businesses worldwide using survey data from 313 respondents. The research revealed that COVID-19 has a significant negative impact on profitability, operations, economics, and access to finance for SMEs. External funding aids have played an important role in SMEs' ability to survive. Dimson et al.⁴⁵⁾ aimed to answer how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted selected areas of management in SMEs in the Czech Republic (CR) and Slovak Republic (SR). The sample included 1502 SMEs, comprising 822 before the pandemic and 680 during it, with 814 from CR and 688 from SR. Results revealed a negative impact on financial performance across both countries. Additionally, 40% of Czech entrepreneurs and 30% of Slovak entrepreneurs believed government economic measures could aid to recovery. Bartik et al.⁴⁶⁾ investigated the impact of COVID-19 on small businesses through a survey of over 5,800 businesses in USA conducted between March 28 and April 4, 2020. Key findings were that mass layoffs and closures just weeks into the crisis, with closure risks negatively associated with the anticipated duration of the pandemic. Many businesses were financially fragile, with the median business having only two weeks of cash reserves. The majority planned to seek financial support through loan but anticipated challenges such as bureaucratic hurdles and eligibility issues. Chen et al.⁴⁷⁾ explore the impact of Covid-19 on Chinese SME and found that 80% of SMEs temporarily closed during initial lockdown. By May 2020, most SMEs had reopened, but many were operating at partial capacity, 19% of them incorporated enterprises and 25% self-employed businesses permanently closed between February and May 2020.

Abuhussein et al.³⁰⁾ study 32 Jordanian SMEs. Using semi-structured interviews, they demonstrate that most SMEs changed their business models to deal with the Covid-19 crisis. These changes included redesigning organizational culture, improving internal communication, and updating their business models to digital ones. Dejardin et al.³¹⁾ study 209 Portuguese SMEs to illustrate that before the pandemic, businesses focused on finding new possibilities, but during the pandemic, their primary goal was to get their goods to market. Similarly, Abhari et al.³²⁾, in the context of Malaysian tourism SMEs, exhibit that the government implemented effective recovery strategies, shaping sustainable solutions, and supporting policies, which had an important role in helping the recovery of small enterprises. Mukherjee et al.³³⁾ identify five crucial factors: the ability to (i) access external resources (ii) reconfigure resources and plan for the long-term objectives (iii) learn entrepreneurial skills to deal with uncertainty (iv) adopt networking and information environment (v) be optimistic for future recovery that helped SMEs overcome the difficulties during the pandemic. A summary of the recent literature presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Selected literature

Author(s) (Year)	Study Focus (Country/ Region)	Key Findings
Sun et al. (2022) ⁵²⁾	Global	COVID-19 negatively impacted profitability, operations, economy, and access to finance for SMEs. External funding aids were crucial for SMEs' persistence through technological innovation
World Bank (2020) ⁵³⁾	13 countries	SMEs experienced greater sales shrinkage and faster cash drain than large firms. Fast-growing SMEs were less affected by demand shocks but more exposed to international trade disruption
Chen et al. (2021) ⁵⁴⁾	China	80% of SMEs temporarily closed during initial lockdown. By May 2020, most SMEs reopened, but many were operating at partial capacity.
Bartik et al. (2020) ⁵⁵⁾	USA	43% of businesses temporarily closed. Active employment reduced by 39% since January 2020

Dimson et al. (2020) ⁵⁶⁾	Europe	Almost 70% of the respondents confirmed revenue decline that caused serious economic consequences in the company. More than half of the respondents expected that their entrepreneurship may be terminated in one year due to the pandemic crisis
Appiah-Kubi et al. (2021) ⁵⁷⁾	Ghana	SMEs experienced a drastic reduction in sales and revenues due to supply chain disruptions and decreased demand.
Nguyen et al. (2021) ⁵⁸⁾	Vietnam	The study showed that the pandemic negatively affected the performance of SMEs in Vietnam, especially in terms of revenue, profit, and employment.
Kowo et al. (2021) ⁵⁹⁾	Nigeria	The study revealed that the pandemic had a significant impact on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria, leading to decreased sales, reduced profitability, and job losses.
Herbane (2020) ⁶⁰⁾	UK	Focused on how SMEs can build resilience to overcome the challenges posed by the pandemic.
Donbesu et al. (2020) ⁶¹⁾	Australia	The study revealed that the pandemic had a significant impact on the performance of SMEs in Australia, leading to decreased sales, reduced profitability, and job losses.

Like other countries, Bangladesh, as a developing country, had a difficulty in dealing with the economic downturn, particularly among SMEs. Hence, few studies focus on the SMEs in Bangladesh. For instance, Islam et al.³⁴⁾ conduct a study and find that most SMEs closed their businesses owing to the lockdown. In addition, one-third of the businesses were obliged to function at a reduced capacity at the start of the pandemic. As a result, their revenues decreased dramatically, as did employment losses. Furthermore, SMEs experienced challenges because of remote work, such as budget constraints, complex processes that slowed down effective action, and a lack of sufficient information about distant workplaces, all of which produced challenges in the communication process. Staffs were also regularly replaced, and a shortage of trustworthy people to conduct remote work disturbed the smooth functioning of businesses³⁵⁾. In addition, Sarker et al.³⁶⁾ demonstrate that demand for goods and services

declined for about 93% of SMEs in Bangladesh. Hossain et al.³⁷⁾ on the other hand, show that the major challenges for SMEs were the cash flow constraint and the supply chain disruption. The research further shows that SMEs turned to incorporating digital transformation for conducting their regular business. However, the task was difficult to implement. For example, Bhuiyan³⁸⁾ reports that 78% of their surveyed SMEs were reluctant to adopt the technology either due to the fear of change or because of the newness of the technologies, for which success was uncertain during the pandemic. Similarly, Karim et al.³⁹⁾ conclude that government-suitable policies for SMEs are essential to ensure their economic resilience after the pandemic. They further argue that to keep SMEs in operation, government stimulus needed to be prioritized. Iqbal et al.⁴⁰⁾ found that large business enterprises were less affected by the pandemic, while SMEs experienced a decline in income.

We build upon and contribute to the above literature by examining the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on the SMEs in Bangladesh. Although the above studies are important in the context of Bangladesh, they rely mostly on a small sample and few selected dimensions including performance, government initiatives, and technology as enhancer of SMEs capability. Our study, however, differs from the above studies in several ways. First, we target a large number of firms as sample which helps us generalize the findings of the research. Second, human resource is an important consideration in business operation. Al-Fadly⁴¹⁾ mentioned that during the covid, SMEs cut up to 20 to 50 percent of its employees. Therefore, we attempt to explore the human resource issues which are very crucial for policymaking but neglected by the current literature. Third, financial assistance from public fund and bank loan played a critical role in SME survival during crisis period. For instance, in Japan, most vulnerable firms survived during the crisis period by using both government financial support programs and banks helps⁴²⁾⁴³⁾. Most studies that focused on Bangladesh SME considered government support, but did not include bank's perspective, which is unique for our study. Finally, the comprehensive coverage of our research would help us offer important policy recommendations.

3. Research Methodology

Several studies have already explored covid crisis and SME. For example, Zou and Li⁴⁸⁾ explained that external factors, government intervention such as lockdowns and restrictions, delay in delivery, logistics and unprecedented demand deficiency significantly impacted SMEs. On the other hand, strong internal capabilities such as diversification, adoptability and proper resource allocation abilities affected SMEs less than other factors. Based on the above discussion, we can develop the analytical

framework below (see Fig 1), where external factors create a challenge for SMEs, and internal factors provide an opportunity to reorganize its internal capabilities to survive in crisis by diversifying its operational and financial process.

Fig. 1: Research framework

Source: Authors creation

The objective of this research is to analyze the impact of Covid-19 on SMEs in Bangladesh. Arnold and Bohner⁴⁹⁾ define impact as a change in activities that influences normal procedures or processes. Recent studies have employed various techniques to examine the effects of the Covid crisis on SMEs. Cuervo-Cazurra⁵⁰⁾ utilized cross-sectional surveys and case studies of SMEs in Latin America, while Martínez-Ros and Orea⁵¹⁾ applied regression analysis using data from Spanish SMEs. Zou and Li⁴⁸⁾ conducted an analysis using China as a case study. This study follows Zou and Li⁴⁸⁾ and taking Bangladesh SME sector as a case study. For this research we take firsthand data collected by an online survey.

A five-part questionnaire was developed based on two research⁶²⁾⁶³⁾ to assess the effects of Covid-19 on SMEs in Dhaka city, Bangladesh. The first part of the questionnaire contains items that are related to basic information about the business. It captures the demographic dynamics of the surveyed SMEs. Part two contains the information related to how the Covid-19 affected SMEs. This part asks entities about the overall impacts of their business owing to Covid-19. The third part of the questionnaire asks respondents specific effects, such as changes in demand, sales, or revenues at different intervals caused by Covid-19. Part four of the questionnaire assesses the impacts of Covid-19 on SMEs' employees and investment. Questions in this section ask the respondents if they were forced to adopt job-cut policies or cancel any planned investment during the Covid-19 pandemic. The final part of the questionnaire aims to assess what financial assistance is required from the financial institutions or government to overcome the adverse effects of Covid-19 on SMEs in Bangladesh.

The questionnaires were circulated online, which has been administered and followed up personally by the authors. A total of 500 questionnaires were circulated, and 318 were received (64%), of which 12 were found incomplete. The

data are tabulated using Excel. We have calculated the mean and standard deviation for questions that are framed applying Likert's 5-point scale. The advantage of such analysis is that it is easy to understand even for readers without deep statistical knowledge. We further calculate the percentage to assess what percentage of the respondents were affected by the pandemic regarding a particular context of the SMEs.

We further check the associations between various variables. Given the nature of the data, we have explored possible dynamics of variables through the regression analysis. We apply the following regression model

$$y_i = c + \beta X_i + \varepsilon_i, i = 1, \dots, N, \varepsilon_i = v_i + u_i \tag{1}$$

Where,

y_i is the perception of individual respondents about a significant decline in income

c indicates the constant

β is the co-efficient of each dependent variable

X_i is a set of dependent variables such as the number of employees of the surveyed SMEs, the number of employees fired by SMEs during the pandemic, the number of SMEs shifted their business online during the pandemic, and the level of liquidity helping SMEs to survive the extended period of pandemic shock.

ε_i is the white noise, assumed to be distributed normally with a mean 0 and standard deviation 1.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1. Demographic dynamics

It is observed in Table 2 that most of the respondents (97%) are male. More than half (57%) of the respondents are aged between 26 and 35 years. The data further indicates that about a half (49%) of the surveyed SMEs are in the retail and trade sectors. The second highest representation in the sample comes from the manufacturing sector, constituting about 11% of the total sample. This is followed by the considerably smaller sectors of tourism and healthcare, representing about 3% and 1%, respectively, in the sample. The moderate representations of the financial services, transportation, education, and entertainment sectors range from 7% to 5%.

Table 2: Respondents' demographic characteristics

Item	Description	n	Percentage (%)
Age of the respondents (years)	Between 18-25	42	14
	Between 26-35	174	57
	Between 36-50	76	25
	More than 50	14	4
Gender of the respondent	Male	298	97
	Female	8	3

Years of Operations	Between 1-3 years	29	9
	Between 4-10 years	77	25
	Between 11-20 yea	164	54
	More than 20 years	36	12
Types of Business	Manufacturing	34	11
	Tourism	9	3
	Healthcare	4	1
	Financial Service	18	6
	Transportation	23	8
	Retail trade	149	49
	Education	17	6
	Others	37	12
No. of employees	Between 1-10	153	50
	Between 10-30	90	30
	Between 30-50	32	10
	More than 50	30	10
Plan to tackle a crisis like the Covid-19	Yes	66	22
	No	240	88

Source: constructed by the author Based on survey data

As far as the employment is concerned, exactly half of these businesses are small, indicating a predominance of small businesses. About 30% of the surveyed SMEs have employees ranging between 11 and 30 persons. Larger firms are not as prevalent in the dataset as smaller ones, with just 10% employing more than 50 people and another 10% of surveyed SMEs having a workforce between 30 and 59 employees, Most SMEs (66%) did not have any specific plan to tackle such a pandemic shock. Only 22% of the SMEs had some sort of preparation to absorb the shock. This underscores the importance of being prepared for any adverse economic and financial shock.

4.2. How did the pandemic affect the SMEs?

Section 2 of the questionnaire asks the respondents about the potential impacts of the Covid-19 on their business. The results are shown in Table 3. It shows that a significant number of SMEs either agree (75%) or strongly agree (17%) to the statement that sale of products and services of the SMEs slowed during the pandemic. The mean of this category is 4.02 (on a 5-point Likert scale), which demonstrates that almost all the surveyed SMEs suffered from a decline in sales and revenues during the pandemic. This finding resonates with the statement that ‘my income decreased significantly’ with a mean score of 4.21, and 82% of the respondents either agree or strongly agree with the statement. This can be attributed to the decline in demand for SMEs goods and services. As many as 87% of the respondents either agree or strongly agree with the

claim that the demand for their products and services declined during the pandemic.

Likewise, there was considerable agreement (78% agree and 14% strongly agree) regarding the production disruption brought about by problems with the supply chain. The mean score of this category is 4.00. Labor concerns were not as significant as supply chain disruption; however, this is significant because 70% of the respondents agree and 11% strongly agree that labor absences caused production disruptions, with a means score of 3.80. Due to the lockdown and adoption of social distance policies, many indoor and outdoor programs were cancelled by the government and private entities. This caused significant trouble for the SMEs, as evidenced by the fact that 70% of the respondents agree and 11% strongly agree with the statement that they suffered damages because of government program suspensions. Moreover, it seems that most SMEs could not recover by themselves, as illustrated by the fact that 85% of the respondents either disagree or strongly disagree that they have recovered the loss, pointing to a lasting financial impact rather than a notable recovery. Furthermore, only very few SMEs were able to transfer their business online (11% either agree or strongly agree with the statement that they had shifted their business online), suggesting that there may be obstacles to digital transformation.

Table 3: How did the pandemic affect your business?

Particulars ¹	SD (%)	D (%)	Neutral (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean
The sale of goods and services declined	2	3	4	75	17	4.02
The production declined due to the disruption of supply chain	2	3	4	78	14	4.00
Production disrupted due to the absence of labor	3	6	9	70	11	3.80
The demand goods/services declined	2	4	6	70	17	3.96
I suffered a damage due to the suspension of government’s program	4	7	8	70	11	3.77
I suffered a loss, but I have recovered	8	77	9	5	1	2.14

I shifted the business online	8	70	11	8	3	2.29
I did not suffer a significant loss	61	29	4	5	1	1.56
My income has increased during the pandemic	12	60	23	4	1	2.23
My income has increased but very little	8	23	47	21	1	2.85
There was no change in income	9	68	18	4	1	2.22
My income decreased but very little	4	10	48	34	3	3.22
My income decreased significantly	3	6	9	33	49	4.21

¹ SD = Strongly disagree; D = Disagree; A= Agree; SA = Strongly agree;

Source: constructed by the authors based on survey data

4.3. The effects of the pandemic

Although part two assesses if the surveyed SMEs suffer from losses during the pandemic, section three aims to ascertain the degree of losses more specifically. Table 4 illustrates how badly the SMEs were impacted during this time by giving insights into the expected loss in sales of goods and services that SMEs faced in 2020. About half of the surveyed SMEs (45%) reported that their business suffered an estimated loss in sales between 31% and 50% compared to the scenario before the pandemic. This indicates that a considerable number of SMEs had been in severe financial setbacks during the early phase of the pandemic. However, a small % (5%) of the surveyed SMEs stated that their sales had declined by less than 10%, demonstrating that some resilience or specific market advantages were available for some SMEs. Conversely, 13% of the surveyed SMEs had sales decline between 50% and 80%, whereas 10% of the SMEs had experienced a decline in sales exceeding 8%, indicating the catastrophic circumstances facing a significant portion of the market. However, 4% of businesses reported no reduction in sales, suggesting that they were completely spared from losses owing to some specific nature of business. It is also interesting to note that 14% of respondents couldn't quantify their losses, which could indicate complicated circumstances for evaluating financial effects in the face of unexpected circumstances or serious data limitations. Considering the above facts, Table 4 illustrates the various degrees of financial difficulties that SMEs in Bangladesh experienced in 2020; most of them experienced significant drops in sales. The monthly demand decline, exhibited in Table 4, shows almost the same pattern as the yearly demand decline.

Table 4: The effects of the pandemic

Item	Description	n	Percentage (%)
Estimated loss in sales of products/services in 2020	<10%	14	5
	11% - 30%	26	9
	31% - 50%	137	45
	51% - 80%	40	13
	> 80%	30	10
	No loss yet	11	4
	Estimation was not possible	43	14
	No repores	2	1
Estimated loss in revenue since the Covid-19 outbreak (in Bangladeshi Taka)	< 200,000	29	20
	200,000-1,000,000	77	37
	1,000,000-2,000,000	164	28
	>2,000,000	36	15
Monthly demand decline of your goods/services compared to same period before the pandemic?	< 10%	21	7
	10% - 25%	65	21
	26% - 50%	150	50
	51% - 75%	47	15
	> 75%	20	7
Estimated loss in sales of products/services in 2020	<10%	14	5
	11% - 30%	26	9
	31% - 50%	137	45

Source: constructed by the authors based on survey data

Table 4 further shows the estimated revenue losses incurred by the surveyed SMEs in terms of Bangladeshi Taka (BDT) since the Covid-19 outbreak. About 37% of SMEs reported losses ranging between BDT 200,000 and 1,000,000, which had a substantial effect on their financial stability. After this, losses ranging between BDT 1 million and 2 million were suffered by 28% of surveyed SMEs, showing a serious financial impact that continued into higher loss brackets. On the contrary, 20% of the surveyed SMEs reported losses of less than BDT 200,000, which may indicate that these businesses were less vulnerable to the public health crisis or more resilient. However, 15% of the surveyed SMEs experienced losses greater than BDT 2 million, indicating a significant financial obstacle for this segment. This revenue loss distribution highlights the different economic toll that Covid-19 has imposed on various enterprises, with many suffering from major financial losses.

4.4. Requirements for assistance from financial institutions and government

As shown earlier, SMEs in Bangladesh suffered severely resulting from the Covid-19 pandemic. This calls for some kind of external assistance to tackle the adverse impact of the pandemic. Besides their own initiatives to combat the crisis, we ask SMEs if their banks, with which they had

business transactions, contacted them for any purpose during the pandemic. Also, we ask if they require any assistance from the state to recover the loss. The results are presented in Table 5, which exhibits that 75% of the surveyed SMEs had heard from their banks regarding the pandemic, indicating that the majority of banks made the effort to get in touch with businesses during this time. On the other hand, 25% of SMEs did not receive any information from banks addressing financial concerns related to the epidemic, meaning that 25% of them were left in the dark. Of those who were contacted, 28% got messages saying the bank would be happy to assist if necessary. This suggests that some institutions adopted initiatives to assist their customers through difficult circumstances. Just 3% of SMEs said banks told them to cut expenses because they were worried about the clients' financial health. It is, however, unfortunate that, despite the pandemic's severe economic effects, 66% of the SMEs reported that banks are likely to cut ties in the future if the client firms' financial health does not improve.

Table 5: Requirements of financial and government assistance

Item	Description	n	Percentage (%)
Did you receive any contact from your bank during the pandemic?	Yes	226	75
	No	76	25
What was the message all about?	Bank wants to help you, if needed	63	28
	Banks are worried about your financial health and asked to reduce cost	7	3
	Banks wanted to sever ties if your financial situation does not improve soon	49	66
Which support measures from the government do you think are most important for your business in tackling the adverse impact of the pandemic?	Suspend or defer taxes, duties and such other expenses	29	10
	Except taxes, exempt other obligations due to the state	18	6
	Increase credit facilities	22	7
	Direct aid from the state	224	74

Change of labor laws	4	1
No support measures are necessary	5	2

Source: constructed by the authors based on survey data

Table 5 further illustrates SMEs' preferences for government assistance programs that are thought to be necessary to combat the pandemic's negative consequences. A resounding 74% of the surveyed SMEs consider direct aid from the state to be the most important kind of support, indicating a strong desire for quick cash to get them through difficult times. A smaller but noteworthy percentage, 10% of SMEs, think it would be crucial to postpone or suspend taxes, levies, and other costs, underscoring worries that responsibilities and cash flow will impede recovery efforts. Another 7% of SMEs highlight that they require more credit facilities, indicating that having access to more funds is essential for continuing operations during economic downturns. A demand for relief from various state-imposed provisions is indicated by the 6% of SMEs that view the exemption of commitments to the state other than taxes as vital. Just 1% of the surveyed SMEs believe that labor regulations should change, presumably to give managers more leeway in managing their workforces when demand varies. However, only two percentage of SMEs think that no assistance measures are required, indicating that most think that government engagement is essential to reducing the economic burden of the pandemic.

4.5. Regression results

To further find the association between various antecedents that affect SMEs' income, we adopt regression analysis techniques. We investigate how SMEs' size (number of employees), online mode of business, liquidity, and human resource reduction affect SMEs' income. The summary statistics of the regression equation are presented in Table 6. It is observed that these four variables can explain 16.5% of the variance in income decline ($R^2 = 0.165$) of our surveyed SMEs. Given the structure of the data, this level of R^2 is considered acceptable. In addition, the model fitness is good as well. For instance, the F value of the model is 14.06 which is significant at 0.00% level, indicating that at least one of the predictor variables is significantly related to the decline in SMEs' income during the pandemic. The model further shows a Durbin-Watson statistic value of 1.518. A statistical value of 2.00 indicates no autocorrelation among the independent variables. However, our derived value is close to 2, suggesting little to no autocorrelation in the residuals. This suggests that the assumption of independent errors is reasonably met. Furthermore, the variance inflation factor (VIF), which measures the multicollinearity problem among the dependent variables,

are reported in the Table. We can see that all of the VIF statistics are just above 1.00 against the acceptable threshold of 4.00. Hence, multicollinearity is not a concern for our regression analysis.

In addition, the assumption for linear regression is that data are normally distributed. To check the normality of the data, we analyze the P-P plot (Appendix A1) of the standardized residuals. The graph shows a fairly linear pattern, indicating that the assumption of normally distributed residuals is reasonably met. A slight deviation from perfect linearity is observed at the extremes but aren't severe enough to invalidate the analysis.

Table 6: Model Summary (Dependent Variable: decline in income)

R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
			R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
0.165	0.154	0.932	0.165	14.060	4	284	0.000	1.518

The Anova Table (Table 7) further confirms the overall significance of the model. For instance, the F-statistics, which is 14.06 is highly significant ($p < 0.000$), again indicating that the model is a good fit for the data.

Table 7: ANOVA (Dependent Variable: decline in income)

Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
48.805	4	12.201	14.060	0.000
246.462	284	0.868		
295.266	288			

Table 8 provides the regression results of the model mentioned in equation 1, showing the impact of each predictor variable on the decline in income of SMEs participated in our survey. As can be seen from the Table, SMEs big in size (proxied by the number of employees) face lower decline in sales revenue shown by a negative coefficient (-0.110) of the number of employees on a decline in SMEs' income. This result suggests that a larger number of employees is associated with a lower income decline for the participating SMEs. This relationship is statistically significant ($p = 0.013$) at less than five percent level of significance. Similarly, we observe that SMEs, which has shifted to online mode of business during the pandemic, experienced a lower decline in income. For instance, a negative coefficient (-0.202) of 'business shifted online' suggests that those SMEs which have been able to shift their business activities online have experienced a lower decline in sales revenue. The coefficient is statistically significant ($p = 0.004$) at one percent level of significance.

We also find a negative effect of SMEs' liquidity that may help them survive during the pandemic on their income decline. For example, the level of SMEs' liquidity reduces the decline of their income, with a coefficient (-0.155). This result indicates that higher liquidity level helped SMEs to counteract the force that negatively affects their

income. The coefficient is statistically significant ($p = 0.001$) at one percent level of significance. On the other hand, SMEs that have fired employees are those that have suffered from a decline in income. The coefficient of the number of employees fired shows a positive sign (0.267), suggesting that SMEs' firing employees is associated with more income decline. This result is statistically significant ($p < 0.000$) at zero percent.

Table 8: Regression results (Dependent Variable: decline in income)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
Constant	5.173	0.256		20.238	0.000		
Number of employees	-0.110	0.044	-0.139	-2.499	0.013	0.954	1.048
Shifted business online	-0.202	0.069	-0.163	-2.919	0.004	0.937	1.067
liquidity	-0.155	0.046	-0.181	-3.330	0.001	0.993	1.007
Fired employees	0.267	0.060	0.245	4.459	0.000	0.973	1.028

5. Recommendation, Limitations of the study and avenues for future research

5.1. Policy recommendation

The above findings, related to the obstacles faced by the SMEs in Bangladesh due to the pandemic, help us identify critical areas for governmental action. For example, the economic shocks that SMEs experience are referred to as a 'supply side shock'. Taking action to reestablish the supply chain as quickly as feasible is something that the government ought to do to solve this situation. This will assist SMEs in acquiring the necessary raw materials in a timely manner and at prices that are fair and reasonable. Moreover, a partnership between SMEs and suppliers can be formed, or local supply chains can be developed to avoid any possible supply chain disruption in the future. In addition, enhancing logistic facilities and transportation infrastructure is likely to cement the resilience of SMEs to encounter any similar challenges in the future.

Regulatory authorities need to prioritize employment protection initiatives, such as subsidies or tax incentives for SMEs that maintained their workforce during the pandemic. Additionally, strategizing a framework for interim employment aid for displaced workers could offer a social safety net and promote re-employment prospects once SMEs commence recovery.

The government needs to find a way to promote investment by implementing fiscal and monetary policies including interest rate cuts, quantitative easing etc. to motivate SMEs to resume capital investments following the pandemic. Facilitating innovation and digital transformation projects may enable these firms to adjust to changing market needs and consumer habits, thereby improving their competitive

advantage.

Finally, SMEs in Bangladesh expect direct government intervention, including aid assistance. They consider it an essential support mechanism, which signifies a vital dependence on government assistance for recovery. Policymakers of the country must devise strategies as to the kind of assistance that can be provided directly so that efficient and transparent allocation of money are ensured. In addition, the government can prioritize SMEs, which are in dire need of assistance. Establishing a definitive system for allocating financial or other assistance considering SMEs business size, sector, and particular obstacles experienced by them will guarantee that assistance is directed to those most in need. Furthermore, improving communication between the government and SMEs could guarantee that firms are informed of available resources and support programs.

5.2. Limitations of the study and avenues for future research

The study has some limitations which provide opportunities for future research. For instance, data of our research confines only to SMEs located in Dhaka city although there are other cities which accommodate many SMEs. Data collected from those big cities may help us understand the dynamics of the pandemic effects on SMEs across the country. In addition, there may be potential selection bias. SMEs that chose to respond may differ systematically from those that did not, perhaps in terms of size, financial health, or digital accessibility. While the sample includes various sectors, the dominance of retail and trade might skew results, making them less generalizable to other sectors. Hence, we urge the readers to carefully generalize the findings of this research. Moreover, future research may focus on complementing our research findings through other means such as focus group discussion and personal interviews. In addition, evidence from other developing countries to identify the similarities and contrast to our research would be beneficial.

6. Conclusions

It is widely accepted that the Novel Coronavirus has precipitated an unparalleled global recession. This recession has impacted all sectors of the economy around the world. However, compared to large organizations, Small and medium-sized enterprises were adversely affected by the crisis. Therefore, this study has made a novel attempt to assess the impact of Covid-19 on SMEs in Bangladesh. In so doing, the study collected data from 306 SMEs for a three months period using semi-structured questionnaire. Data are then analyzed using graphical presentation, descriptive statistics, and regression techniques. The following are the major findings

First, it has been found that the majority of the surveyed SMEs reported a loss in sales due to a decline in demand for firms' goods and services. In addition, supply chain disruption created an upward pressure on production and distribution of SMEs' goods and services. Second, the pandemic has forced more than one third of the surveyed Bangladeshi SMEs to dismiss employees, underscoring an urgency for job security and the welfare of different strata of workers. Third, the findings that 92% of the surveyed MSEs halted or completely suspended their planned investment in direct response to the pandemic indicate a substantial reduction in future growth potential. Fourth, the SMEs' shift to online mode of business, liquidity strength to survive the pandemic shock, and large size in terms of the number of employees helped the surveyed SMEs to mitigate the negative effects of the pandemic on their income.

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Appendix

Figure A1: Test of normality

SME Impact Assessment for COVID-19

The purpose of this survey is to obtain first-hand information on how SMEs operate during the COVID-19. Your input will help us identify problems, constraints and challenges to improve the government’s comprehensive response strategy, deploy resources to address critical business needs and develop new policies to significantly improve SME legislation in the country.

The information provided in this survey will be kept strictly confidential and please note that there is no right or wrong answers.

Thank you for your contribution!

Sincerely,

The Research Team

1. In which industry or sector, you operate your business? Please tick one.

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|----------------|--------------------------|-------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Manufacturing | <input type="checkbox"/> | Tourism |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Health service | <input type="checkbox"/> | Finance |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Transportation | <input type="checkbox"/> | Sales and retail |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Education | <input type="checkbox"/> | Others (please specify) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Entertainment | | |

2. How many employees does your company have? Please tick one.

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|-----------------|--------------------------|-----------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Self-employed | <input type="checkbox"/> | Between 31 - 50 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 10 | <input type="checkbox"/> | 51 or more |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Between 10 – 30 | | |

3. Does your business already feel repercussions due to the COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Yes, I experience a loss of goods and services	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, I experience lost output due to supply chain disruption	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, I experience lost output due to medical leave of my employees	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, I experience less demand of my products and services	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, due to cancelation of public events	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, I have losses but I was able to compensate those by reducing costs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, I have also opted for doing my business online	<input type="checkbox"/>				
No, I do not experience any repercussion at the present moment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Yes, revenues have increased substantially	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, revenues have increased a little	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, revenues have stayed the same	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, revenues have reduced a little	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yes, revenues have reduced	<input type="checkbox"/>				

substantially

Yes, we will be as stronger than before Covid

Yes, we will try to keep going, but there's a good chance we may have to close

Yes, I'm pretty sure we will have to close the business

Yes, we already know that we cannot continue trading after this

4. Does your business have an action plan / is well prepared for crisis scenarios of similar scale? Please tick one.

- No
 Yes
 No assessment is possible at the present moment

5. Do you expect as a consequence of COVID-19 a loss of sales in products / services in 2020? Please tick one.

- Yes, a minimal loss of sales (less than 10%)
 Yes, a major loss of sales (more than 10%)
 More than 30%
 More than 50%
 More than 80%
 No, I do not expect a loss of sales
 No assessment is possible at the present moment
 Other (please specify) _____

6. What is your loss in revenue since the COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

- Less than 1000 OMR
 Between 1001 – 4999 OMR
 Between 5000 – 9999 OMR
 10000 OMR or more

7. What is your expected loss in revenue in the next 2 months due to COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

- Less than 1000 OMR
 Between 1001 – 4999 OMR
 Between 5000 – 9999 OMR
 10000 OMR or more

8. What is the demand for your goods/services compared to last year? Please tick one.

- Less than 10.0% Between 50.01 – 75.0%
 Between 10.01 – 25.0% 75.01% or more
 Between 25.01 – 50.0%

9. Were you forced to dismiss/send home a number of your employees? Please tick one.

- I had to terminate employment (s)
 No, I did not have to terminate employment (s)
 I could not prolong fixed-term contract (s)
 I had to put employee (s) on short-time work

10. How many employees you had to layoffs since the COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------|--------------------------|--------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 0 | <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 30 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 40 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 5 | <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 50 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 10 | <input type="checkbox"/> | 50 or more |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 20 | | |

11. How many employees you will have to lay off in the next two months due to the COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------|--------------------------|--------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 0 | <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 30 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 40 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 5 | <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 50 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 10 | <input type="checkbox"/> | 50 or more |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Less than 20 | | |

12. Were you planning on new employments or accepting apprenticeship before the COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

- Yes No

13. Did you cancel any planned investment in your company's infrastructure and/or production due to the COVID-19 outbreak? Please tick one.

- No
 Yes
 Your comment (optional)

14. If the situation continues/does not improve soon, for how many weeks do you have financial liquidity until you have to stop your business activities or declare bankruptcy? Please tick one.

- 1-2 weeks
 3-4 weeks
 up to 2 months
 more than 2 months
 up to 6 months
 up to 12 months
 more than 12 months

15. Have you been contacted by your bank in connection with COVID-19? Please tick one.

- Yes No

16. If yes, what was their message? Please tick one.

- We will help you. Take it easy.
 We are concerned. Turn down production and cut operations.
 We are closing our cooperation with you.
 Not applicable

17. Which support measures do you think are most necessary in the current situation? (you may tick several boxes if necessary).

- Deferral of taxes, duties and other expenses
- Exception of taxes, duties and other expense-related obligations
- Enlargement of your credits by your bank or financial institute
- Direct state aid
- Change of labour laws
- No support measures are necessary at the present moment
- Other (please specify) _____

18. Please comment on how the above-stated measures will impact the development of your business. Please tick one.

- Will keep my business afloat but still need to employ / retire stuff
- Will enable to keep my business floating as it is
- Other (please specify) _____

19. Anything else you would like to add or suggest?

Thank you for completing our survey!